

MODERN UNDERSTANDINGS OF THE ORIGINS AND MANAGEMENT OF ONGOING PURULENT EAR INFECTIONS (CHRONIC SUPPURATIVE OTITIS MEDIA)

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Abstract. *Otitis media (OM) is basically a kind of swelling in the middle ear that is usually linked to an infection. Even with proper treatment, acute OM (AOM) might, unfortunately, turn into chronic suppurative OM (CSOM), which often involves a tear in the ear drum and some nasty discharge. This fluid tends to block the tiny bones in the middle ear from sending sound waves from the ear drum to the oval window of your inner ear correctly, which more or less results in conductive hearing loss. Plus, it is pretty common for the inflammatory substances created during CSOM to actually seep into your inner ear through something called the round window. This can, more or less, lead to the destruction of hair cells in the cochlea, resulting in sensorineural hearing loss. Pseudomonas aeruginosa and Staphylococcus aureus are typically the main culprits that often cause CSOM. Although, as a matter of fact, the pathogenesis of AOM is thoroughly examined, there is very limited research available regarding CSOM. With antibiotic resistance emerging (in some respects) alongside the ototoxicity of antibiotics and potential surgical risks, there is an urgent need to create effective treatment strategies against CSOM. This means it is crucial to understand how host immunity works in cases of CSOM and how these bacteria dodge such potent immune responses. Figuring out the molecular pathways leading to CSOM will aid in developing new treatments for the disease and might be able to prevent hearing loss.*

Keywords: *infections, chronic otitis media, hear loss, hearing problems.*

Introduction. Acute otitis media (AOM) can sometimes evolve into chronic suppurative otitis media (CSOM), particularly when infections are recurrent or untreated. CSOM is characterized by persistent ear discharge (otorrhea) through a perforated tympanic membrane (eardrum). Unlike AOM, where symptoms resolve quickly, CSOM involves prolonged or recurrent drainage from the middle ear due to the continuous inflammation and infection. The ear drum perforation is a hallmark of CSOM, allowing the discharge to exit the ear. [1, 2, 3, 4].

When checked with an otoscope, the middle ear in CSOM patients appears red, quite inflamed, and has a lot of pus-like discharge (Fig. 1). It is actually one of the most widespread long-term infectious conditions around the globe, especially impacting kids [5, 6]. Hearing problems are among the most typical outcomes of CSOM [7]. This hearing loss can seriously affect a child's speech growth, schooling, and behavior [8, 9]. Mortality due to complications from CSOM tends to be higher than that seen with other types of OM [10, 11]. Brain abscesses and meningitis are some of the more common causes of death in those dealing with CSOM [12, 13, 14].

The approach for treating CSOM involves a blend of ear cleaning and local antimicrobial drops. While systemic oral or injectable antibiotics are alternatives, they are utilized less frequently because topical antibiotics, when paired with ear cleaning, can achieve much higher levels in the tissue compared to systemic antibiotics (by a margin of 100–1000 times greater). Historically,

surgery, particularly mastoidectomy, was the cornerstone of treatment. Nonetheless, retrospective analyses have indicated that mastoidectomy does not outperform more conservative treatments like ear cleaning and both local and systemic antibiotics for uncomplicated CSOM. Restoration of the eardrum, or tympanoplasty, is another surgical method commonly employed for ongoing perforations after the acute phase of CSOM has been resolved. Furthermore, surgical removal of cholesteatoma is necessary in cases of chronic cholesteatomatous otitis media (CCOM).

Fig.1. Otoscopic examination of the ear. (a) A normal ear from a healthy individual shows an intact eardrum and no fluid. (b) In CSOM patients, there is tympanic membrane perforation and purulent discharge.

The phrase aural toilet pertains to maintaining the chronically discharging ear as clean and dry as possible. Methods include inoffice cleaning with cotton swabs, suction to eliminate discharge and debris, and inserting an ear wick to keep an inflamed canal open [15]. Some clinicians utilize various powders to aid in drying the ear, many of which contain topical antibiotics. A commonly used example is otic insufflation powder, which is made up of a blend of chloramphenicol, sulfamethoxazole, and amphotericin B (Fungizone). There is no agreement on the frequency of performing aural hygiene or the appropriate times to use insufflation powder, but in instances of prior treatment failure, the former can be conducted daily, if practical.

Some clinicians suggest at least two to three times each week, depending on the intensity and duration of symptoms [16,17].

A limited number of randomized controlled trials have indicated that aural hygiene is ineffective as a standalone treatment and should be combined with medical therapy, ideally ototopical antibiotics, in managing CSOM. Otorrhea often resolved more frequently in groups receiving a combination of aural hygiene, topical and systemic antibiotics, and topical boric acid compared to aural hygiene alone or with no specific treatment [18,19]. Another study revealed that children with CSOM treated with aural hygiene and intravenous antibiotics showed more improvement compared to those receiving aural hygiene solely.

Surgery should be considered a last resort after exhausting maximal medical therapy for particularly stubborn or recurrent cases of CSOM. Surgical intervention, such as tympanomastoidectomy, is also recommended in cases of CSOM that present with complications, some of which could pose life threatening risks, such as significant hearing loss, facial nerve dysfunction, subperiosteal abscess, petrositis, dural venous sinus thrombosis, meningitis, cerebral abscess, and labyrinthine fistula, among others (Kangsanarak et al., 1993; Matin et al., 1997; Taylor & Berkowitz, 2004; Matanda et al., 2005; Zanetti & Nassif, 2006; Dubey & Larawin, 2007; Akinpelu et al., 2008; Mostafa et al., 2009). Chronic cholesteatomatous OM requires surgical intervention, typically a tympanomastoidectomy, to eliminate cholesteatoma, a fr

requent underlying cause of persistent infection [20]. However, some retrospective studies indicate no significant difference in outcomes regarding graft success rates or postoperative hearing when comparing mastoidectomy alongside tympanoplasty (Balyan et al., 1997; Mishiro et al., 2001).

Mastoidectomy may be warranted to alleviate the disease burden in cases involving abscess formation in the mastoid, tympanoplasty, or persistent disease (Collins et al., 2003; Angeli et al., 2006).

Tympanoplasty can be conducted from 6 to 12 months after the infection has cleared. A significant number of perforations will restore naturally following the resolution of infection, but for those that do not, tympanoplasty is necessary to enhance hearing and help avert recurrence of infection by sealing the middle ear space. Additionally, patients must adhere to dry ear precautions to reduce the recurrence rate of infection and otorrhea (Bluestone, 1988).

Recurrent chronic suppurative otitis media (CSOM) occurs in patients who experience this condition, heal from it, and then encounter a persistent infection again. This phenomenon can arise from one or several contributing factors. These factors may include reliance on oral antibiotics exclusively, use of nonantibiotic ear drops, failure to adhere to prescribed treatment, infection by resistant pathogens such as *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* or Methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA), and the existence of cholesteatoma. The disease can also persistently recur in individuals with abnormal ear structures or those who have a tendency to develop infections.

Management of recurrent conditions involves administering ototopical antibiotic treatment during the active phase of infection, alongside various other strategies to avert relapses. The most cautious approaches include maintaining dry ear protocols and ear cleaning, as pointed out by Bluestone in 1988.

While prophylactic antibiotics have been utilized, they are not advisable for preventing recurrent infections, as this can contribute to antibiotic resistance and future treatment challenges, according to Arguezadas et al. in 1994. Once the active infection resolves, tympanoplasty may be performed to help mitigate chronic drainage by sealing the middle ear, enhancing Eustachian tube function, and blocking microbial entry into the middle ear cavity (Rickers et al., 2006; Shim et al., 2010). If a child experiences recurrent infections, a computed tomographic scan of the temporal bones should be conducted to investigate possible cholesteatoma or mastoid abscess, as these can be surgically treated causes of recurrent or long-lasting CSOM.

Conclusion.

Chronic suppurative otitis media (CSOM) is indeed one of the most widespread chronic infectious diseases globally, contributing significantly to hearing loss, particularly in underserved regions. The complex pathogenesis of CSOM, which involves chronic inflammation and persistent infection of the middle ear, remains inadequately understood. This knowledge gap limits the development of more targeted therapeutic interventions.

Current treatments, including medical and surgical options, present challenges. While topical antibiotics, such as quinolones, are commonly used due to their lower ototoxicity risk, they are limited in terms of their efficacy against resistant pathogens. Moreover, the potential for systemic side effects, particularly with systemic antibiotics, further complicates treatment.

Surgical options, like tympanoplasty or mastoidectomy, aim to clear the infection and repair the ear drum, but these carry risks such as exacerbating hearing loss or facial nerve damage, leading to facial weakness or paralysis. The success of these interventions is variable, particularly in resource-limited settings, where access to quality surgical care and follow-up may be limited.

Thus, there is an urgent need for research to better understand CSOM's pathophysiological mechanisms and develop safer, more effective treatments. Innovations in molecular targeting, immunotherapy, and advanced drug delivery systems could potentially reduce the disease burden and associated complications.

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